

Tea-time: Study of factors affecting organic matter decomposition in water - STUDY PLAN

Aim

I want to find out the effects of the water-related factors (pH, Electrical Conductivity, saltiness) and different types of tea on underwater decomposition of plant matter.

Background

Carbon cycling is a process of decomposition which releases carbon dioxide and thus contributes to climate change. We want to find out where carbon cycling happens faster and where it happens slower and what water and organic matter parameters affect this process. There are many studies about organic matter decomposition in terrestrial systems (soil), but not much is known about carbon cycling underwater. My study will help to fill in this knowledge gap.

Questions

- How does water pH affect the decomposition rates?
- How does water saltiness affect decomposition rates?
- How does water electric conductivity affect decomposition rates?
- How will different types of organic matter affect decomposition rates?

Hypotheses

- I hypothesise that when the pH is too low or too high it will slow down the decomposition.
- I hypothesise If there is a lot of salt it will slow down the decomposition.
- I hypothesise that the more electric conductivity will speed up the decomposition.
- I hypothesise that some types of organic matter will decompose slower and some will decompose faster. Specifically, tea with higher protein content should decompose faster.

Methods

Experiment 1

Collect water samples in bottles from lakes, ponds and streams, 4L from each. Measure the pH, total saltines, and Electric Conductivity in the water using a digital sensor-pen.

Weight and label 2 types of tea bags (Rooibos and Green tea).

Put each tea bag in a plastic zip-lock bag and add 100 ml of water.

Put it in a place with stable room temperature, in darkness.

Wait 3 months.

Collect, dry and check decomposition by weighing dried tea bags.

Experiment 2

Collect 8L of water from a clean natural stream.

Measure the pH, saltines, and Electric Conductivity in the water.

Prepare 5-8 different types of tea with the same type of tea bag.

Find the protein, fat, carbohydrates and salt content of each tea type and label all the tea bags.

Put each tea bag in a plastic zip-lock bag and add 100 ml of water.

Put it in a place with stable room temperature, in darkness.

Wait 3 months.

Collect, dry and check decomposition by weighing dried tea bags.

Equipment / materials

Experiment 1 (pH, EC and water saltines)

Plastic bag 40x5 = 200

Permanent marker = 1

Green tea 20x5 = 100

Rooibos tea 20x5 = 100

Weighing tray/metal muffin cup = 200

Electronic scale = 1

Electronic sensor for pH, Electric Conductivity and Total Salt = 1

Scissors, sellotape, pen, notebook

Experiment 2 (Different type of tea)

Plastic bag

Permanent marker x1

Rooibos tea x10

Green tea x10

Chiran tea x10

Houji tea x10

Earl grey tea x10

Hibiscus and rose hip x10

Jasmien tea x10

Weighing tray / metal muffin cup

Electronic sensor for pH, Electric Conductivity and Total Salt = 1

Scissors, sellotape, pen, notebook